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Competency-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of trading enterprises in the conditions of digitalization and change management

Relevance of the research topic. *The study of the competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of trading enterprises in the conditions of digitalization and change management is conditioned by the lack of a single approach to the implementation of the algorithm of this process.*

Formulation of the problem. *The evolution of the application of various leadership systems has shown both positive and negative aspects of their application, and this is a natural process, as the factors and conditions of production change in the practice of organizational management. At the moment, there are several modern models of leadership development, in particular, a competency-oriented approach. Enterprises independently develop the type of this model, in particular due to their branch affiliation. Competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of specifically trading enterprises in the conditions of digitization and change management is not sufficiently studied, which determines the relevance of the research topic.*

Setting the purpose and objectives of the study – *to investigate a competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of trade enterprises in the conditions of digitalization and change management.*

Research method or methodology. *The article uses the following methods: monographic, analysis and synthesis, systematization.*

Presentation of the main material (research results). *Studies have shown that the functioning of an effective system of leadership formation is an important strategic task, as it directly affects the formation of an employee as an active subject of production, interested in increasing the efficiency of his work. The decisive factors of the leadership system should be: satisfaction of material needs to achieve a certain level of well-being; increasing the prestige of work; increasing the level of mechanization and automation of work, etc. All these components build up and motivate employees to high labor activity and increased labor productivity.*

Field of application of results. *The results of the study can be used in the practical activities of trading enterprises to improve the competence-oriented approach in the leadership system in the conditions of digitization and change management.*

Conclusions on the article. *After developing a project of an effective mechanism for the formation and use of a competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of trade enterprises, it is necessary to conduct its analysis by experts. Company employees (managers, managers and specialists) and involved consultants can act as experts. And only after finalizing the mechanism in accordance with the received comments and suggestions, all necessary provisions and orders are issued. In practice, you should always reach a certain compromise that takes into account the requirements of a specific situation in terms of digitalization and change management.*

Keywords: *competence-oriented approach, leadership system, trade enterprises, digitalization, change management.*

Компетентісно–орієнтований підхід у системі лідеротворення торгових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації та управління змінами

Актуальність теми дослідження. Дослідження питання компетентісно–орієнтованого підходу у системі лідеротворення торгових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації та управління змінами обумовлюється відсутністю єдиного підходу до реалізації алгоритму даного процесу.

Постановка проблеми. Еволюція застосування різноманітних систем лідеротворення показала як позитивні, так і негативні аспекти їх застосування, і це природній процес, так як на практиці управління організацією міняються фактори та умови виробництва. На даний момент існують кілька сучасних моделей лідеротворення, зокрема компетентісно–орієнтований підхід. Підприємства самостійно розробляють тип даної моделі, зокрема через свою галузеву приналежність. Компетентісно–орієнтований підхід у системі лідеротворення конкретно торгових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації та управління змінами не є достатньо вивченим, що і обумовлює актуальність теми дослідження.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – дослідити компетентісно–орієнтований підхід у системі лідеротворення торгових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації та управління змінами.

Метод або методологія дослідження. В статті використано наступні методи: монографічний, аналізу і синтезу, систематизації.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). Дослідження показали, що функціонування ефективної системи лідеротворення є важливим стратегічним завданням, оскільки воно безпосередньо впливає на становлення працівника як активного суб'єкта виробництва, зацікавленого в підвищенні ефективності своєї праці. Вирішальними чинниками системи лідеротворення мають бути: задоволення матеріальних потреб для досягнення певного рівня добробуту; посилення престижності праці; підвищення рівня механізації і автоматизації робіт тощо. Всі ці складові набудовують і спонукають працівників до високої трудової активності і зростання продуктивності праці.

Галузь застосування результатів. Результати дослідження можуть бути використані в практичній діяльності торгових підприємств для вдосконалення компетентісно–орієнтованого підходу у системі лідеротворення в умовах діджиталізації та управління змінами.

Висновки за статтею. Після розробки проекту ефективного механізму формування та використання компетентісно–орієнтованого підходу у системі лідеротворення торгових підприємств необхідно провести його аналіз експертами. У ролі експертів можуть виступати працівники підприємства (керівник, менеджери та спеціалісти) та залучені консультанти. І лише після доопрацювання механізму відповідно до отриманих зауважень та пропозицій видаються всі необхідні положення та накази. На практиці слід завжди досягати певного компромісу, що враховує вимоги конкретної ситуації в умовах діджиталізації та управління змінами.

Ключові слова: компетентісно–орієнтований підхід, система лідеротворення, торгові підприємства, діджиталізація, управління змінами.

Statement of the problem in a general form and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. The evolution of the application of various leadership systems has shown both positive and negative aspects of their application, and this is a natural process, as the factors and conditions of production change in the practice of organizational management. At the moment, there are several modern models of leadership development, in particular, a competency-oriented approach. Enterprises

independently develop the type of this model, in particular due to their branch affiliation. Competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of specifically trading enterprises in the conditions of digitization and change management is not sufficiently studied, which determines the relevance of the research topic.

Analysis of the latest research and publications, in which the solution to this problem was initiated and on which the author relies,

selection of previously unsolved parts of the general problem, to which the article is devoted.

Policy in the field of leadership development of trading enterprises in most cases has two goals:

1) promote the desire of employees to work more productively;

2) increase the stability of economic relations.

The system of material interest should be like a system of investing in the quality of personnel. Low employee motivation can lead to negative consequences: a drop in labor productivity, a deterioration of the social and psychological climate in the team, a decrease in the quality of work, a deterioration of the company's image on the market, and as a result, a decrease in the efficiency of the company and its profit.

The directions of leadership formation of trading enterprises in the system of economic relations in the conditions of digitalization and change management can be oriented in the following directions:

1. Technocratic – overcoming the crisis of the development strategy, changing the management structure;

2. Adaptive – focused on smoothing out contradictions when limited by time frames.

When describing the leadership system, it is important to take into account the following indicators: the level of satisfaction with the trading company of the workplace, the level of average wages, the composition of the staff according to the socio-demographic structure, the availability of benefits, the distance from the transport network.

From the above, it can be concluded that the optimal system of leadership formation must comply with the following principles:

1. The salary must be sufficient, that is, the worker must earn enough to ensure the satisfaction of his needs at a level not less than the subsistence minimum. Otherwise, the employee will look for additional ways to earn income.

2. The development and implementation of a system of payment «by category» of employees with the introduction of a minimum amount, below which salaries at this enterprise do not fall, can ensure sufficient remuneration.

3. The level of wages with a variable component must be competitive on the labor market. The fact of salary increase motivates employees to a loyal attitude towards the company, the fact of increasing the variable component – to productive work, achieving higher results.

4. Remuneration must be perceived by employees as fair. The criteria for evaluating the performance of employees and the achievement of results must be recorded in the local regulations of the enterprise, known to the employees and easily measured. If the employee is unable to accurately determine the amount of his salary, he will consider it to be underpaid. A complex payroll system does not allow the employee to plan his budget, which leads to additional costs and, as a result, causes dissatisfaction with his salary.

Salary directly correlates with the possibility of applying a competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of trade enterprises in the conditions of digitalization and change management.

Setting the purpose and objectives of the study – to investigate a competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of trade enterprises in the conditions of digitalization and change management.

Presentation of the main material of the study with a full justification of the obtained scientific results. As the experience of the largest competitive domestic and Western trade enterprises shows, today the tasks of the personnel service cannot be limited to solving only the current tasks of recruitment, accounting, retraining, and dismissal of personnel. They should move to the level of development and implementation of strategic approaches to personnel management in terms of implementing systems for improving the labor potential of enterprises, coordinating all aspects of personnel management, mastering modern technologies for studying the labor market and their involvement, creating an effective system for monitoring, diagnosing and forecasting labor potential, introduction of a system of socio-psychological analysis and planning, prevention of intra-company conflicts, creation of an effective system of training and professional growth of employees and a modern system of personnel motivation, leadership development and others.

Practice shows that the improvement of the personnel management system should be aimed at: developing a strategy and tactics for managing labor resources; personnel planning and marketing; recruitment, selection, hiring and accounting of personnel; labor organization and regulation of labor processes; building an effective staff motivation system; social insurance and social security; personnel development management; improvement of

methodical, organizational and information support of the labor potential management system; organization of personnel audits and controlling; labor relations management; implementation of a competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation, as well as promotion of the development of corporate culture at the enterprise.

The main management functions with personnel development should be delegated to the Bureau of Labor Organization and Wages: development of personnel strategy and tactics; organization of staff training; its assessment, attestation and certification; personnel movement management; planning, marketing, professional orientation and staff adaptation; management of social and labor relations in the team and others.

Studies have shown that the functioning of an effective system of leadership formation is an important strategic task, as it directly affects the formation of an employee as an active subject of production, interested in increasing the efficiency of his work. The decisive factors of the leadership system should be: satisfaction of material needs to achieve a certain level of well-being; increasing the prestige of work; increasing the level of mechanization and automation of work; creation of an extensive network of social infrastructure facilities in the area; psychological awareness of the need for the work to be performed and the feeling of a real owner of the property. All these components build up and motivate employees to high labor activity and increased labor productivity.

Determining the priority areas of leadership development of trade enterprises is the main condition for the formation of labor resources.

One of the most important factors in the formation of the personnel of trade enterprises can be carried out only on the basis of a comprehensive approach that uses both material and non-material methods of increasing the interest of employees in improving their quality characteristics. In this regard, it is necessary to develop proposals for the further development of the use of all tools for motivating the personnel of a trading enterprise. Certain methods, techniques and types of motivation are used at each stage of labor management.

At the stage of career guidance and adaptation, it is necessary to stimulate the assimilation of new employees into the team by creating a favorable atmosphere in the team by creating a mentoring

system, it is also advisable to consolidate the employees' understanding of the relationship between competence and the amount of remuneration.

At the training stage, it is necessary to stimulate employees to improve their qualification level and learn new professions by creating favorable conditions for training (paying for advanced training courses, providing the opportunity for internships, providing the opportunity to be separated from production for a session if employees are studying by correspondence), the use of material resources and moral incentives for workers who have improved their qualifications or are learning new professions.

At the stage of evaluation of labor activity, the motivational function of the stage should be ensured in those cases when the evaluation is used to make decisions about promotion on the career ladder or for material reward.

In addition to the motivation of labor resources at the main stages of their management, it is necessary to constantly stimulate them to self-improvement, using bonus systems and providing the opportunity to apply personal abilities at work.

Determining the priority areas of motivation of labor resources is the main condition of leadership formation. In this study, employees of trade enterprises were interviewed about the main factors that affect the efficiency of the performance of labor functions.

The most acceptable is an innovative type of personnel training, the purpose of which is to create an orientation towards renewal. The most difficult point in the learning process is mastering the methods of independent acquisition of knowledge. Using various methods of development, it is possible to manage the competence of personnel (Table).

Today there is a new innovative approach in the system of leadership development of trade enterprises. This is a new technology in personnel training, which is called a business retreat. In English, the word retreat means «solitude», «removal from society». A retreat is a certain format of human interaction. Many perceive a retreat as simply a form of organizing a space for learning.

The idea of the «Business Retreat» project is that during a certain break from everyday reality, being outside the city in nature in beautiful conditions, the participants receive not only business technologies for the successful realization of themselves as managers and owners, but also some core within them-

Modern methods of development of personnel of a trading enterprise

Method	Description, possibility of use
Training	A minimum of information and a maximum of exercises to practice skills. It is used to develop skills in a small group of people
Case Studies	Interactive technology for short-term training of managers based on business situations. The goal is to teach how to analyze information, sort it to solve a given task, identify key problems, and choose the optimal solution
Coaching	A new form of consulting support, a means of facilitation, assistance in finding solutions or overcoming any difficult situation. The task of a coach is not to give knowledge or skills, but to help a person find them independently and consolidate them in practice
E-learning	Mass method of distance learning. In the form of e-books, video lessons, computer exercises. Efficiency is manifested in the transfer of knowledge to a large number of people
Self-study	It takes place individually under the condition of stimulation, it is studied using a variety of materials: books, documentation, audio, video and multimedia programs that are taught

selves, a new look at familiar things and circumstances. There is an understanding of what is happening, a competent interaction strategy is developed. As a result, there are internal conflicts and stresses, new resources and motivation for achievement appear, new horizons and opportunities open up.

For the effective implementation of the personnel development strategy and capital investments in the company's personnel, employee loyalty is of primary importance.

The concept of «loyal» comes from the French word «lojal» – devoted. Staff loyalty is understood as a benevolent, correct, private, sincere, respectful attitude towards management, employees, their actions and towards the enterprise as a whole; conscious performance by an employee of his work in accordance with the purpose and tasks of the enterprise and in its interests, as well as compliance with norms, rules and obligations, including informal ones, in relation to the enterprise, management, employees and other subjects of interaction.

You can also use modern Mystery Shopping technology to check staff loyalty. The methodology involves the involvement of a number of agents, whose task is to simulate external contact, and to evaluate the actions of personnel in the process of carrying out the operation. With the help of this technology, you can find out how loyal the staff is to their employer, how honest and reliable employees are, whether they are not committing illegal and immoral actions that can cause damage to the well-being of the business. The reaction of the company's personnel to the offer of bribes, «kickbacks», to provocative requests to carry out work «by the cash register», to carry out operations based on forged documents, to disclose commercial secrets, etc., is becoming known. In this way, you can see which of

your employees you can trust, and who should be classified as a potential risk group.

In the conditions of digitization and change management, there is a serious struggle for professionals. The management of every trading company understands that success largely depends on the qualifications of employees. In-house training does not always solve the problem, especially if specialists are needed «here and now». A real way out of the current situation is provided by the use of such a recruitment technology as headhunting, which involves a targeted search and attraction of the most valuable and promising personnel.

Headhunting is a rare and, at the same time, very promising method of selecting particularly valuable, «artificial» specialists. To date, this is perhaps the most effective technology, which was formed in response to the need for exclusive candidates for the positions of top managers and key specialists.

In the modern practice of external selection of candidates, the following technologies are mainly used: screening, recruiting and headhunting.

Screening is a «superficial selection» that is carried out on formal grounds: education, age, gender, work experience. Low vacancies are usually closed through screening.

Recruiting is an «in-depth selection» that takes into account the applicant's personal characteristics and business qualities. It is carried out by recruiting agencies for the selection of mid-level specialists.

Headhunting is a «quality search» that takes into account the specifics of the customer's business, work environment, business and personal qualities of the candidate, organized directly.

More recently, Ukrainian companies understood the word «automation» to be programs only for the organization of sales and accounting. For five years

now, there have been modules for keeping personnel records of employees and calculating wages. And only three years ago, HR functionality appeared in some systems, but at an initial level.

Today, more and more commercial enterprises are implementing automated management systems. And the field of HR is no exception. The main software products for the field of HR are: the StaffManager program of the Mainstream company; «ABBY Ukraine»; «E-Staff, WebTutor» of the Koloris company.

Further, for effective personnel management, it is necessary to develop a personnel coordination mechanism. This system will allocate and redistribute employees within one trade enterprise during the labor process, which is especially relevant for enterprises with high seasonality of production; carry out measures to prevent the appearance of problems, eliminate disruptions in the production process, analyze and eliminate the causes, as well as improve the mechanism in the conditions of digitalization and change management.

Conclusions from this study and prospects for further research in this direction. After developing a project of an effective mechanism for the formation and use of a competence-oriented approach in the system of leadership formation of trade enterprises, it is necessary to conduct its analysis by experts. Company employees (managers, managers and specialists) and involved consultants can act as experts. And only after finalizing the mechanism in accordance with the received comments and suggestions, all necessary provisions and orders are issued. After implementation, an analysis of the efficiency of the mechanism is carried out, in the case of an unsatisfactory result, the reasons, their analysis and correction of the mistakes and shortcomings are identified. When analyzing efficiency, it should be understood that there is no unequivocal correspondence between economy and profitability. Highly economical management can be ineffective in terms of achieving the goal itself, divert from it, and effective – uneconomical if the goal will be achieved at too high a cost. Therefore, in practice, you should always reach a certain compromise that takes into account the requirements of a specific situation in terms of digitalization and change management.

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